

pH Titration Curves of Some Uttar Pradesh Soil Clays in Aqueous Hydrochloric Acid Medium

G. SINGH, SHARAFAT ALI, D. PALIT and S. K. DE

Department of Chemistry, University of Allahabad, Allahabad

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The buffering capacity of fourteen (14) soil clays obtained from twelve different soils of U.P. (India) has been determined in simple hydrochloric acid medium. The maximum buffering capacity shown by the different soil clay-hydrochloric-acid systems has been found to lie in the following order :

Varanasi old alluvium clay > Acid clay > Kanpur old alluvium clay > Kabar clay > Kanpur recent Alluvium clay > Rakar clay > Parwa clay > Alkali clay > Varanasi recent alluvium clay > Mar clay > Vindhyan clay > Tarai clay > Hill clay > Bhabar clay.

The buffering property of clay minerals constituting the different soil clays is assigned primarily to the OH-groups present in the alumina octahedra and silica-tetrahedra sheets of the clay minerals. pH of the soil clays appear to influence this buffering property in the sense that soil clays of higher pH consume less of alkali (except Tarai clay which consumes comparatively more alkali though it is having high pH value).

THE buffering capacity of soils and the nature of charge in the soil colloids were determined with the technique of titration curves. Bremner¹ working with different soil clays observed that the buffering capacity depends upon their reacting colloidal material and the property is exhibited on

both sides of pH 7.0. The amphoteric property of soils can thus be established. Schofield² discussed the nature of electrical charge on clay particles from their titration curves. Puri *et al*³ published a series of papers on the titration curves of soils and humus with different alkalies and in presence of different

Fig. 1.

- pH titration of 0.01N HCl system with 0.01N NaOH.
- pH titration of old alluvium clay (Varanasi) system with 0.01N NaOH.
- ▲—▲— pH titration of acid soil clay with 0.01N NaOH.

Fig. 2.

- (X)—(X)— pH titration of 0.01N HCl system with 0.01N NaOH.
- (O)—(O)— pH titration of old alluvium soil clay (Kanpur) system with 0.01N NaOH.
- (Δ)—(Δ)— pH titration of Kabar soil clay system 0.01N NaOH.

Fig. 3.

- (X)—(X)— pH titration of 0.01N HCl system with 0.01N NaOH.
- (O)—(O)— pH titration of recent alluvium soil clay (Kanpur) system with 0.01N NaOH.
- (Δ)—(Δ)— pH titration of Rakar soil clay system with 0.01N NaOH.

Fig. 4.

- ⊗—⊗— pH titration of 0.01N HCl system with 0.01N NaOH.
- pH titration of Parwa soil clay system with 0.01N NaOH.
- △—△— pH titration of Alkali soil clay system with 0.01N NaOH.

Fig. 5.

- ⊗—⊗— pH titration of 0.01N HCl system with 0.01N NaOH.
- pH titration on recent alluvium soil clay (Varanasi) system with 0.01N NaOH.
- △—△— pH titration of Mar Soil clay system with 0.01N NaOH.

Fig. 6.

- pH titration of 0.01N HCl system with 0.01N NaOH.
- pH titration of Vindhyan soil clay system with 0.01N NaOH.
- △—△— pH titration of Tarai soil clay system with 0.01N NaOH.

Fig. 7.

- pH titration of 0.01N HCl system with 0.01N NaOH.
- pH titration of Hill soil clay system with 0.01N NaOH.
- △—△— pH titration of Bhabar soil clay system with 0.01N NaOH.

neutral salts. The titration curves of a sample of clay separated from a typical Bengal soil was discussed by Mukherjee and Mitra⁴ and thus observed the effect of the salt concentration and the bases used for titration. De and Srivastava⁵ studied the question whether or not the rapid titration curves for non-equilibrated acid-soil water systems with a few treatments could be useful for isolating the factors which induce buffering property of the soil. Quite recently, De and co-workers^{6,7} studied the buffering capacity of soils, clay minerals and clay mineral mixtures in citric and hydrochloric acid media.

It appears from the above brief resume that the works relating to buffering capacity of some U.P. soil clays are still to be determined in simple hydrochloric-acid medium. The present work is, therefore, undertaken to determine which of the U.P. soil clays has greater buffering capacity in the said acid system.

Experimental

Fourteen soil clay samples belonging to Hill soil, Bhabar soil, Vindhyan soil, Kanpur recent alluvium, Kanpur old alluvium, Varanasi recent alluvium, Varanasi old alluvium, Rakar soil, Parwa soil, Mar soil, Kabar soil, Acid soil and Alkali soil have been taken for the study of their buffering capacity in aqueous muriatic acid medium.

For the titration, 2 g. soil clay were taken in 10 ml. of 0.01N HCl in 250 ml Corning beaker and shaken well. It was then titrated (without allowing it to reach equilibrium) with 0.01N NaOH and the

The quantity of 0.01N NaOH consumed by the different clays in 0.01N HCl under similar conditions was taken as the buffering capacity of the system. A blank determination in a similar fashion was also done with 0.01N HCl.

The soil clays were chemically analysed by the reported methods^{8,9}. The values obtained are given in Table 1.

Straight line equations between the pH (log) attained in HCl-soil clay systems and the volume of 0.01N NaOH (log) added in the system (Table 3) was also obtained and discussed here.

Results and Discussion

A perusal of Figs. 1 to 7 clearly shows the buffering capacity of 14 soil clays in 0.01N muriatic acid medium. It has been observed that the Varanasi soil alluvium soil clay exhibited the maximum buffering capacity followed by acid soil clay and the lowest position in relation to the buffering capacity has been occupied by Bhabar soil clay (Table 2). Further, the buffering capacity of different soil clays has been found in the following decreasing order.

Varanasi old alluvium > Acid clay > Kanpur old alluvium > Kabar clay > Kanpur recent alluvium > Rakar clay > Parwa clay > Alkali clay > Varanasi recent alluvium > Mar clay > Vindhyan clay > Tarai clay > Hill clay > Bhabar clay.

It is interesting to note that when the values of the change of pH with the addition of 0.01N NaOH

TABLE 1. CHEMICAL COMPOSITION OF SOIL-CLAYS

Soil clay	Total SiO ₂ %	Total Fe ₂ O ₃ %	Total Al ₂ O ₃ %	Total R ₂ O ₃ %	C/N ratio	Total C.E.C. m.e./100 g.	pH	Ratio		
								SiO ₂ /R ₂ O ₃	SiO ₂ /Al ₂ O ₃	SiO ₂ /Fe ₂ O ₃
1. Varanasi oil alluvium	50.25	10.40	16.88	27.40	11.80	28.62	7.1	1.83	2.97	1.62
2. Acid clay	64.12	9.60	6.29	15.20	8.23	43.40	6.6	4.22	10.66	6.66
3. Kanpur old alluvium	42.61	11.20	24.18	35.60	8.40	34.44	7.5	1.20	1.76	2.16
4. Kabar clay	58.62	7.90	14.78	22.90	19.01	59.02	7.5	2.86	3.96	1.95
5. Kanpur recent alluvium	45.60	11.20	18.11	29.40	19.07	40.24	7.8	1.55	2.52	1.62
6. Rakar clay	54.13	7.20	18.97	26.20	11.90	36.12	7.8	2.07	3.85	2.63
7. Parwa clay	46.13	18.39	12.28	30.80	13.36	40.82	8.1	1.49	3.75	2.66
8. Alkali clay	52.70	8.80	13.71	22.70	3.60	38.64	9.5	2.32	3.84	1.56
9. Varanasi recent alluvium	42.76	11.20	21.75	33.20	7.90	36.72	7.9	1.29	1.96	1.94
10. Mar clay	43.89	7.99	21.48	29.60	4.20	62.13	8.4	1.48	2.04	2.69
11. Vindhyan clay	50.54	10.40	20.27	30.70	36.07	36.82	7.8	1.65	2.49	1.95
12. Tarai clay	38.32	19.20	16.99	36.20	36.22	46.36	10.9	1.20	2.26	1.88
13. Hill clay	50.46	9.80	20.84	30.70	43.70	38.62	7.8	1.64	2.42	1.47
14. Bhabar clay	48.53	9.20	9.20	30.06	45.25	36.72	7.6	1.62	2.33	2.26

pH was recorded after addition of every one ml. of 0.01N NaOH. The pH was noted accordingly till it was found to be constant. In other words, the addition of 0.01N NaOH was continued in a similar fashion till the pH of the system was found to be 11.40 which was the pH observed for 0.01N NaOH.

are plotted in their logarithmic scale, a straight-line relationship is obtained between the two values. The straight line equations obtained between the two values are shown in Table 3. The importance of such equations is this that comparisons can be made between two or more soils of the region about their

TABLE 2. TOTAL ml. OF 0.01N NaOH CONSUMED BY THE DIFFERENT SOIL CLAYS TO BRING THE pH TO 11.40. pH of 0.01N NaOH = 11.40

Soil Clay	ml of 0.01N NaOH consumed
Varanasi old alluvium	166
Acid soil	163
Kanpur old alluvium	157
Kabar soil	154
Kanpur recent alluvium	147
Rakar soil	145
Parwa soil	144
Alkali soil	142
Varanasi recent alluvium	139
Mar soil	136
Vindhyan Soil	117
Tarai soil	86
Hill soil	82
Bhabar soil	73
ml. of 0.01N HCl	72

buffering capacity from such buffering capacity equations.

TABLE 3. STRAIGHT LINE EQUATIONS SHOWING THE RELATIONSHIPS BETWEEN pH (LOG) ATTAINED IN AQUEOUS HCl-SOIL CLAY SYSTEMS WITH THE ADDITION OF ml. OF 0.01 N NaOH ADDED (LOG)

Soil clay	Straight line equation
Old alluvium (Varanasi)	Y = 0.2126X + 0.80
Acid soil	Y = 0.1584X + 0.79
Old Alluvium (Kanpur)	Y = 0.2035X + 0.76
Kabar soil	Y = 0.2309X + 0.80
Recent Alluvium (Kanpur)	Y = 0.0875X + 0.90
Rakar soil	Y = 0.2217X + 0.80
Parwa soil	Y = 0.1944X + 0.70
Alkali soil	Y = 0.0175X + 0.98
Recent Alluvium (Varanasi)	Y = 0.1228X + 0.90
Mar soil	Y = 0.0875X + 0.90
Vindhyan Soil	Y = 0.1763X + 0.75
Tarai soil	Y = 0.0087X + 0.95
Hill soil	Y = 0.2443X + 0.56
Bhabar soil	Y = 0.0875X + 0.87

N.B.—Y = pH(log) and X = Volume of 0.01N NaOH added (log).

The explanation given by Schofield² for the buffering capacity of soils on or below pH 7.0 may also be applied here to explain the buffering property of soil clays. This is especially so with the Varanasi

old alluvium soil clay (pH 7.1) and acid soil clay (pH 6.6) which exhibit higher buffering capacity in comparison to the other soil clays. Incidentally, it may be pointed out here that clay minerals are commonly present in the inorganic colloidal fraction of the soil. Accordingly, the explanation provided by Schofield² for such reactions may also be applied here :

The reactions are of the nature of exchange dissociation of H⁺, OH⁻ and subsequent replacement of the cation i.e., Na⁺. Reaction (i) which is more prominent towards acidic side is gradually replaced by reaction, (ii) as increasing amounts of OH⁻ ions are added to the titrable media. In this connection, it may be pointed out that the clay minerals (here present in soil clays) contain OH⁻ groups in their alumina-octahedra or silica-tetrahedra sheets which are said to be responsible for exhibiting buffering properties⁹.

The order of buffering capacity of the different soil clays was not found to have any clear correlation with their different chemical constituents. There appears however, that the extent of pH values of the soil clay has some influence on the sequence of their buffering property. A soil clay of lower pH value appear to consume more of the alkali than a higher pH soil clay.

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